

1 Irf6 is associated with visual activity dependent transcription in vertebrates.

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We recovered in a microarray-based expression screen to identify genes associated with vision and
8 blindness using a vertebrate model light-dependent visual field activity. We specifically sought to discover
9 genes associated with visual field activity-dependent transcription in the vertebrate CNS. We identified Irf6
10 as a candidate regulator of light (i.e., visual field activity) -dependent transcription in the vertebrate retina.

11 In mice, in the skin in vivo, Irf6 deletion resulted in modest activation of the gene encoding the
12 medium-wave-sensitive opsin 1 (cone pigments), *Opn1mw*, indicating sequence-specific precision control
13 of transcription associated with visual field activity by Irf6 in the central nervous system was possible.

14 GSE5800

15 Citations

16 1. Kondo, S., Schutte, B.C., Richardson, R.J., Bjork, B.C., Knight, A.S., Watanabe, Y., Howard, E.,
17 Ferreira de Lima, R.L., Daack-Hirsch, S., Sander, A. and McDonald-McGinn, D.M., 2002. Mutations in
18 IRF6 cause Van der Woude and popliteal pterygium syndromes. *Nature genetics*, 32(2), pp.285-289.

19 2. Richardson, R.J., Dixon, J., Malhotra, S., Hardman, M.J., Knowles, L., Boot-Handford, R.P.,
20 Shore, P., Whitmarsh, A. and Dixon, M.J., 2006. Irf6 is a key determinant of the keratinocyte
21 proliferation-differentiation switch. *Nature genetics*, 38(11), pp.1329-1334.

22 3. Rahimov, F., Marazita, M.L., Visel, A., Cooper, M.E., Hitchler, M.J., Rubini, M., Domann, F.E.,
23 Govil, M., Christensen, K., Bille, C. and Melbye, M., 2008. Disruption of an AP-2 α binding site in an IRF6
24 enhancer is associated with cleft lip. *Nature genetics*, 40(11), pp.1341-1347.